

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable D2.8 Arctic Window of Copernicus
The Arctic PASSION perspective

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Executive summary

Arctic PASSION is contributing to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. It aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge. It also aims at streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services and contribute to ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system.

In the call that Arctic PASSION responded to, it was specifically stated that an Arctic Window of Copernicus should be established. No details were provided by the EU stakeholders on what this should be, but the project learned that Copernicus had started development of Copernicus Hubs, including a Copernicus Arctic Hub. To fully understand the landscape of Copernicus services, Arctic PASSION performed an analysis of Copernicus services, their interoperability and potential products of relevance for the Arctic. Main findings of this report is that Copernicus services from an interoperability perspective are highly heterogeneous making it hard to integrate the Copernicus data in decision support systems.

The ideas outlined in this document support the idea that users should have the opportunity to find and look at relevant Copernicus products, but also be able to integrate these into existing value chains, processing environments or decision support systems. In this context this document suggests extensions of functionality in the Copernicus Arctic Hub. Improvements in functionality the project think will increase the impact of Copernicus data. These improvements will require modifications in existing data documentation (e.g. discovery metadata, to make them suitable for machine interpretation) and web services. If such changes are not possible, it should be considered to evaluate Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem for this purpose as this already implements some of the requirements identified.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The key motivation of the Arctic PASSION project is to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. It aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge. It also aims at streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services and contribute to ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system.

In the call that Arctic PASSION responded to, it was specifically stated that an Arctic Window of Copernicus should be established. Arctic PASSION included this perspective in the Data Management Plan (RD-1). No details were provided by the EU stakeholders on what this should be. In the aftermath of that call, Copernicus began establishing a number of thematic hubs, among these is the Copernicus Arctic Hub. Development of this thematic hub is being coordinated by Mercator Ocean International. An attempt to establish a collaboration with mutual information exchange did not succeed at first. Meanwhile, the Arctic PASSION team continued with preparing an unofficial document describing what the Arctic Window of Copernicus could be like. After discussion with commission representatives and Mercator Ocean International (MOI) that is responsible for the Copernicus Arctic Hub, a decision was made that the Arctic Window of Copernicus as such would not be implemented and the Copernicus Arctic Hub will continue. It was also decided, that the unofficial document contains important views and ideas and should become an official document. Through a contract amendment of the Arctic PASSION contract this became deliverable D2.8 and replaced the action of implementing the Arctic Window of Copernicus.

In the preparations to establishing the Arctic Window of Copernicus, an analysis of Copernicus services, their interoperability and potential products of relevance for the Arctic was developed (RD-2). Main findings of this report is that Copernicus services from an interoperability perspective are highly heterogeneous making it hard to integrate the Copernicus data in decision support systems. Most services do not follow any interoperability standards and although one could expect Copernicus services, being a European initiative, to comply with the INSPIRE framework (RD-3) for exchange of spatial data, this is not the situation. Establishing a unified view on the data is thus a costly and maybe not sustainable approach.

This document provides an overview of the Arctic PASSION activity concerning an Arctic Window of Copernicus, the requirements identified and suggested way forward by the Arctic PASSION team.

1.2. Description of interoperability issues

The deliverable D2.2 “Report on the interoperability status of Copernicus services in light of EU regulations and Polar Data System” (RD-2) lists the key findings as follows:

- “The COPERNICUS and national level services provide hundreds of Earth Observation (EO), geospatial and geoscientific datasets that are relevant for the Arctic PASSION project and the Arctic dimension in general.”
 - Various COPERNICUS services provide data catalogues that are not compatible with geospatial
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standards such as OAI-MPH and OGC CSW.

- The catalogues in different COPERNICUS services are not usually compatible with each other.
- Not all data are listed in machine-readable catalogues with machine readable discovery metadata but need manual intervention to be found.
- The data access APIs are also usually not compatible with geospatial standards such as OGC or OPeNDAP.
- As in the case with data catalogues, the APIs of different COPERNICUS services are not compatible with each other.
- Some relevant datasets are not even online.
- WekEo is an attempt to address the previous issues. Even though the data catalogue in WEkEO adheres to geospatial standard (OGC CSW) the data API (HDA API) does not and the information provided through OGC CSW is not sufficient for direct integration of datasets in decision support systems used by the users.

To summarize, the positive side is that a huge volume of relevant data is made available and can be searched for and downloaded by the user. WEkEO is also a good attempt to rectify the issues mentioned.

On the negative side a lot of manual work is needed to actually use the Copernicus data even through WekEo. Also, integrating the data into value chains is difficult. This needs to be done on a service basis. Usage of data in such value chains requires setting up tailored downloading, transforming and ingestion systems by the user. For example, in QGIS software it is possible to integrate various data sources just by using their remote addresses through e.g. a catalogue service (e.g. OGC CSW). This is not easily achieved with WEkEO for example.

1.3. On the roles of the Arctic Hub and the Arctic Window

The Copernicus Arctic Hub is developed within WekEo and is mostly a graphical representation of data. Direct access to data seems to be of less priority, except unless the user moves the usage into the processing environment embedded in the platform. This processing environment is a commercial service and is disconnected from existing value chains the user could have. This approach is beneficial for a certain type of user group that just want to access data quickly and get an overview of the situation.

The Arctic Window of Copernicus within Arctic PASSION was originally developed with a slightly different point of view in mind. The idea was to make the relevant data to Arctic region to be easily accessed by standardised APIs for geospatial, both for data discovery and data access.

This does not imply that the graphical representation of Copernicus products nor the processing environment offered within the Copernicus Arctic Hub is irrelevant to some user groups.

1.4. Scope

The purpose of this document is to capture requirements for the Arctic Window of Copernicus from the Arctic PASSION perspective and to ensure coordination of the efforts developing the Arctic Window of Copernicus Services and the Copernicus Arctic Hub.

1.5. Applicable documents

- RD-1** D2.1 - Data Management Plan
- RD-2** D2.2 - Report on the interoperability status of Copernicus services in light of EU regulations and Polar Data System
- RD-3** INSPIRE Directive
- RD-4** D2.3 - Website with data information, description of available and emerging web services and user client to find data regardless their location and regular updates on datasets that have been FAIRfied

2. Coordination with other activities

When Arctic PASSION responded to the call there was no information on parallel processes for the Arctic Window of Copernicus.

In 2022 it came to the knowledge of Arctic PASSION that Mercator Ocean International (MOI), as lead entity for Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS) had received that task to develop the Copernicus Arctic Hub. Following this a dialogue between Arctic PASSION and MOI on the Arctic Window of Copernicus was established. A number of coordination meetings were arranged, but no information on the requirements nor plans could be shared with Arctic PASSION by MOI. In December 2023, the [Copernicus Arctic HUB](https://www.arctic.hub.copernicus.eu/) [https://www.arctic.hub.copernicus.eu/] was launched. The data viewer seems similar to the viewer in the Coastal hub.

In the current evaluation of the hubs it is evident that both contain a web GIS viewer of relevant products with an ability to interactively request and download products. Furthermore there are discovery metadata records available for manual download in the viewers as XML and JSON. The granularity of these records are still to be analysed.

There is an API interface (Harmonised Data Access) for download as well, but this is, as also discovered in [RD-2](#) a non standardised interface lacking a catalogue interface for true machine treatment. Utilisation of a non standardised interface will leave the data consumer to add support for the interface instead of relying on off the shelf functionality supporting standardised API's like OGC and OPeNDAP.

NOTE

The interactive interface is nice and appealing, but cumbersome if a large volume of data is needed. As well as if data is to be integrated into an existing decision support system (or viewer) of choice of the data consumer. The latter is the situation for most established decision support processes as these processes are combining many types of data, not only Copernicus data.

In April 2024 the Commission decided that the Copernicus Arctic Hub will continue and the Arctic Window of Copernicus will be implemented. This deliverable D2.8 replace the action of setting up the Arctic Window.

3. Requirements

The call Arctic PASSION responded to had no details on expectations or requirements for a Arctic Window of Copernicus. As result, the requirements definition was left to Arctic PASSION. Following this, Arctic PASSION has tried to identify a number of requirements to fulfil in the Arctic PASSION perspective of the Arctic Window of Copernicus.

From the perspective of Arctic PASSION, the main design criteria of the Arctic Window of Copernicus should have included:

1. relevant Copernicus data for the Arctic region,
2. utilization of standardized API's^[1] to make the data available and possible to integrate in decision support systems of the consumers choice,
3. data accessible in a coherent and easy to access manner including the assurance of data traceability by fully referencing source data sets

In the Arctic PASSION project these goals are further elaborated in documents D2.1 “Data Management Plan” (living document, [RD-1](#)) and D2.2 “Report on the interoperability status of Copernicus services in light of EU regulations and Polar Data System” ([RD-2](#)). The outcome of these documents is that there are already a great number of datasets available for the Arctic region and multiple COPERNICUS (or national) interfaces to access the data. However, identifying the most relevant datasets among the wealth of data is a meticulous process. In addition, accessing the data is also complicated because of the multiple data catalogs, interfaces, and standards being used, as well as heterogeneous granularity of discovery metadata records.

NOTE

The purpose of the Arctic Window of Copernicus was to overcome these difficulties and offer the end user a concise and clear way to visualize and eventually download information.

Specific requirements are listed below.

- REQ-1** A unified view of Copernicus products in a web map client **must** be established.
- REQ-2** The data behind the visual interpretation (**REQ-1**) **should** be available for download/access (see [RD-2](#) for availability issues) including references to the source data to assure reproducibility.
- REQ-3** Copernicus products **should** be possible to integrate in existing decision support systems and value chains by standardised API's.
- REQ-4** All machine interfaces (API's) **must** follow a formal standard allowing efficient reuse of software solutions across data sources and providers. I.e. standards that are used in larger frameworks like INSPIRE and not self defined RESTful interfaces. This applies both to discovery and data services. See [RD-4](#) for Arctic PASSION perspectives on this.

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- REQ-5** Discovery metadata **must** follow a standard and be served through standardised interfaces with direct references to the web services serving the data embedded in the discovery metadata (see [RD-4](#) for Arctic PASSION perspectives on this).
 - REQ-6** Discovery metadata **must** have a granularity and structure that allows machine handling of the information and integration in various decision support systems.
 - REQ-7** Data **must** be encoded in a FAIR compliant data format.
 - REQ-8** Data **must** be served through FAIR compliant services.
 - REQ-9** Server side data selection/reduction services **should** be offered to simplify data integration.

The above mentioned requirements will support both interactive exploration of the data as well as machine integration into existing decision support systems and value chains. Over the last decade or so there has been a push in Europe towards pulling users into platforms for analysis/interpretation of data (e.g. the DIAS concept, EOSC). This has been a mixed success. Part of the reason is that decision processes relies on many products, they also often follow well established work flows and rely on specific tools and hardware as identified by the owner of the decision chain. These decision support systems and value chains are targeted at the use cases of the owner and typically integrates various types data, including data of origin that is not available or possible to make available in the platforms. The emerging platforms are setup to support a wide variety of users, ranging from expert users to policy makers, but also often rely on business and cost models that are changing. [REQ-3](#) and [REQ-4](#) are thus widening the footprint of the Copernicus data to also allow integration in existing value chains in a cost efficient manner and does not seek to change existing value chains which is much harder. Adhering to the INSPIRE directive would greatly simplify reuse of the Copernicus data in this context. [REQ-5](#) and [REQ-6](#) ensures integration is possible without human intervention. This is a requirement for cost efficient and sustained integration. [REQ-9](#) ensures server side data reduction and selection, enabling manageable volumes of data to be transferred to the consumer and reducing the bandwidth consumption. The reason for this is that often data consumers seldom use the full dataset in the decision process they run.

NOTE

The closer to the policy makers the user community, the more need for dedicated aggregated products that analyses the content provided by the Copernicus services. In essence this implies that the interfaces provided has to be dedicated to different user communities. These user communities are not sufficiently identified yet.

4. Analysis of requirements

4.1. Background

The requirements identified above were used in an analysis to find out how they could be implemented. Originally this was focused around implementation within Arctic PASSION, but as information about the Copernicus Arctic Hub became available, focus shifted towards existing activities and how these could support the intention identified. This is further discussed below.

4.2. Minimum Viable System (MVP) of the Arctic Window of Copernicus

Arctic PASSION has established a unified catalogue of datasets through integration of discovery metadata from various data repositories (RD-4). This is available at <https://data.arcticobserving.org/>. The SAON data catalogue acts as a broker between various discovery metadata formats and supports a number of machine interfaces to the content. Currently it has no Copernicus data available, but it addresses some of the requirements identified above. It has limited visualisation functionality, but relies on comprehensive discovery metadata that let computers integrate data.

The first step to implement the Arctic Window of Copernicus was to develop the Minimum Viable Product (MVP). The goal for MVP was to have:

1. an overview of datasets to integrate (ideally through a catalogue setup),
2. API's serving data (allowing consumption of data, either quantitative or qualitative through visualisation),
3. a viewer that unifies the data sources for easy viewing access.

According to document RD-2, the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards are the most used standards with the COPERNICUS interfaces. OGC Web Map Service (WMS) is often used for visualization of geospatial data (for example, satellite images). Also according to RD-2, Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) and Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET) make available their national data using OGC WMS. For this reason, OGC WMS is a promising candidate as backend in the MVP for graphical representation of gridded products. For the Copernicus datasets identified in RD-1, it is possible to establish a mediator containing OGC WMS of some relevant datasets, but this would require direct access to the data. Such a mediator backend can support COPERNICUS services in case the COPERNICUS service doesn't offer web map services for consumption.

The MVP needs a frontend that can consume OGC WMS for the data visualization. A basic viewer can be established using basic building blocks such as OpenLayers or Leaflet. Ideally the MVP and external users are using the same backend service for graphical representation of the products. Prioritisation of services could be done through dedicated servers for the internal services while public services where there is less knowledge on traffic patterns have lower priority. Building the MVP on the Copernicus Arctic Hub is preferable provided resources are available for the development team to develop the machine services indicated. The viewer developed within Arctic PASSION for the Pilot Service State of the Arctic Environment, by GRID-Arendal is also an option, but lacks sustainable funding. There is a simple WMS viewer in the data catalogue (RD-4) set up by Arctic PASSION, but this is created for a limited use case compared to the one identified and could only be considered a fallback solution if nothing else is possible. If comprehensive and detailed discovery metadata following the requirements indicated above are made available this would allow for further integration of these products into decision support systems of the users choice.

In pursuing an approach for MVP, Arctic PASSION has tried to coordinate with the development team of the Copernicus Arctic Hub. This effort is briefly described in Section 2. The Copernicus Arctic Hub is mainly a viewer that provides an overview of the datasets using a WebGIS solution. It has limited functionality for machine and interactive downloading datasets, and no catalogue machine interface, nor does it follow standards and the maps in the WebGIS solution is not available for external users.

Some of these aspects are analysed more carefully in [Section 4.3](#). The proposed way with the MVP is as follows:

1. Establish sufficiently detailed discovery metadata for a limited set of Copernicus products (see [RD-1](#)).
2. Integrate these records in a machine readable catalogue (addressing granularity issues that prevents direct integration in value chains).
3. Provide public (or reuse if already available somewhere) OGC WMS layers for the relevant datasets and integrate this information in the discovery metadata.
4. Configure the viewer to use the machine readable catalogue and through this OGC WMS GetCapabilities.

The approach above would at least allow users to integrate Copernicus products in their existing value chains (in particular decision support systems) that rely on visual interpretation of products.

The data catalogue setup for Arctic PASSION could be used as an example (selected datasets) of a machine readable data catalogue that allows direct integration into decision support systems.

4.3. From visualization to data access in the Arctic Window of Copernicus

On a general basis the Copernicus Discovery metadata records evaluated so far have issues on granularity, semantic annotation and application of interoperability standards that prevents fully automated machine utilisation of the datasets.

There are also viable alternatives to OGC CSW for discovery metadata (e.g. OAI-PMH, OpenSearch, OGC API Records, DCAT-AP, schema.org etc.). In practice, it will require less efforts to build the Arctic Window of Copernicus on already implemented technologies.

As mentioned above a machine readable data catalogue is required to properly integrate Copernicus data into existing value chains and decision processes. Such a service is already implemented by Arctic PASSION through the SAON data portal which is currently available at <https://data.arcticobserving.org/>. This uses SolR as the catalogue backend and has support for OAI-PMH, OGC CSW and OpenSearch^[2]. Within 2025 support for OGC API Records and STAC will be added. The setup is based on pycsw and a collaboration with OSGeo to improve the integration between pycsw and SolR is planned in 2025.

The MVP system described in this document is first and foremost to illustrate and visualize the gridded Earth Observation (EO) datasets. All arctic data is not EO raster data though. There are many in situ measurements that are timeseries at points, trajectories, profiles or trajectories of profiles as well as outlines (e.g. ice charts). These data has to be handled differently in particular speaking of graphical representation. The Copernicus services also provide such data but usually not in a standardized way ([RD-2](#)).

In the context of INSPIRE, data access has been addressed through OGC web services. However the current valid INSPIRE technology stack is based on older versions of the OGC services. OGC CSW is used for dataset discovery, OGC WFS and WCS for data download and WMS for visualisation. While OGC WMS is good visualisation of gridded data as maps, it is not suitable for visualisation of non gridded data like timeseries, trajectories, profiles etc. OGC WFS can serve both point and vector data, so at least for

visualization purposes OGC WFS servers (like Geoserver) can act as the backend for bringing in *in situ* data for the Arctic Window. Another option for this is where data are served through OPeNDAP, then automated visualisation of time series, trajectories etc can be offered through streaming of data.

In the context of Arctic PASSION the data catalogue already contain discovery metadata to point information (e.g. time series at stations), trajectories (e.g. surface buoys), profiles (e.g. CTD casts, radiosondes) etc extracted from WMO GTS (and other sources like SIOS) and served as CF-NetCDF through OPeNDAP. However, for this to work in practise the frontend (the viewer) must be capable of rendering the information provided from backends (whether this is OGC WFS, OPeNDAP or in the future OGC EDR). These capabilities have to be further analysed, but e.g. there are applications developed in the context of Arctic PASSION for e.g. visualisation of timeseries of climate indicators for sea ice (see e.g. <https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index-monthly> or <https://cryo.met.no/en/sea-ice-index-daily>) that could be adapted and reused.

In the Copernicus context the WEkEO platform is the central service to access the data distributed over different COPERNICUS services. From the point of view of the Arctic Window of Copernicus, WEkEO as a framework is in its current form not optimal. There are several reasons for this. First since, as mentioned above, there are no machine interfaces allowing users to bring Copernicus data in existing value chains, processing environments and decision support systems. Instead the idea is that users should move their value chains etc into the environment offered through WekEo. This is unlikely to happen as most value chains etc are not relying on Copernicus data alone, but combine these with other data. Thus it has to be made interoperable at the machine level, implying that data access mechanisms has to be added. For this to be useful, discovery metadata granularity has to be addressed, since the discovery metadata are the information used by any value chain or decision support system to decide on which data to integrate into the process. Current structure of these records within Copernicus is clearly made for interactive use and not machine use.

In a modern context the user should be able to extract the data for a specific location (bounding box or polygon) and for certain time periods. With EO data it is not often practical at all to download the entire dataset. From the user point of view, it is preferable that user requests the region and time, and server side will provide him/her exactly that.

All machine interaction with Copernicus data must be based on standardised interfaces allowing reuse of software for different purposes. It is not scalable for users to develop software for many API's to access and integrate Copernicus data. It was also the intention of the INSPIRE directive that this framework should ensure standardised access to data and information about data across data providers.

In Europe today there are many parallel developments of access mechanisms for data and information. We did mention INSPIRE above, which is based on OGC web services. However in other context e.g. the OpenEO API is used. Currently, it is in fast paced development, and it is getting foothold in the geospatial community. The OpenEO is intended to unify the access to different API's and cloud services of EO data with the idea in mind that the user shouldn't need to download complete datasets just to access a small part of it. OpenEO is not yet a standard but aims to be one. Like the WekEo API (HDA), OpenEO is also REST based. Another option is the long used standard OPeNDAP which also is a RESTful service and already in use by several Copernicus services in their backends. A rather new solution to gaining foothold rapidly is also SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC). Like OpenEO the STAC is also REST API. STAC provides API for catalogue, data search and access. The downside of the STAC is that it can be made OGC compliant, but all the STAC implementations are not such by default. This could mean problems for the automated retrieval of data, or customizing work for various data sources and efficient reuse of

existing infrastructure at the data consumer side.

Recently the Copernicus services have started to disseminate EO data using [Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem](https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/) [https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/] or CDSE for short. For instance, the GlobLand products are being introduced to CDSE. The system has a vast range of API's mentioned also in this document. For catalogue search CDSE offers:

1. OData
2. STAC
3. OpenSearch
4. Sentinel Hub Catalog API

And for data access:

1. OpenEO API
2. OGC API (WMS/WMTS/WFS/WCS)

In addition CDSE provides cloud computing possibilities for both accessing and processing the data on the server side.

However, If other Copernicus services also migrate to CDSE then it is obvious that many of the proposed ideas in this document are already implemented. The CDSE APIs adhere to geospatial standards, allowing direct integration of data into existing value chains etc. The CDSE doesn't provide visualization services although the Sentinel Hub services offer seamless integration with QGIS Software. It might be possible to even use CDSE as backend for the Arctic Hub of Copernicus if development of machine end points are difficult in the WekEo framework.

5. Summary

One of the goals of Arctic PASSION project was to establish the Arctic Window of Copernicus. I.e. to provide relevant Copernicus data to the Arctic regions through a web portal. The work began by identifying relevant datasets [RD-1](#) and analysing the interoperability status of the Copernicus services [RD-2](#). During the course of the project it became apparent that the Copernicus Arctic Hub was a parallel effort with similar goals. The commission decided that duplication of efforts should not happen and since the long term perspective of the Copernicus Arctic Hub is guaranteed contrary for Arctic PASSION that is a limited duration project, it make sense to focus development on the Copernicus Arctic Hub. The ideas outlined in this document support the idea that users should have the opportunity to find and look at relevant Copernicus products, but also be able to integrate these into existing value chains, processing environments or decision support systems. In this context this document suggests extensions of functionality in the Copernicus Arctic Hub. Improvements in functionality the project think will increase the impact of Copernicus data. These improvements will require modifications in existing data documentation (e.g. discovery metadata) and web services. If such changes are not possible, it should be considered to evaluate Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem for this purpose as this already implements some of the requirements identified. However this will also require some further modification.

[1] Simplifying reuse in decision support systems and value chains.

[2] Service not identified as the location of the service will change in 2025, an identical example is available through <https://adc.csw.met.no/>.